

The impact of social loafing on team performance with the mediating role of network of relationships

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Abstract— Teams in organizations with the help of synergy can create the capacity to better adapt the organization to the environment and results with better performance outcomes. Effective teams are considered successful for many organizations, which cannot be done by one person, and improve the performance of the organization. While these teams may be more productive than individuals, there is considerable evidence that teams necessarily are not as productive as they seem. One of the negative aspects of teamwork is the tendency of people to put in less effort when working in a group, known as Social Loafing. The main purpose of this research was to study the impact of Social Loafing on Team Performance in EdTech (Education Technology) companies located in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. In addition, the present study deals with the mediating role of Network of Relationships. Data for this study was collected using a fully structured among 180 teams of EdTech companies. Findings shows that Social Loafing impacts the performance of knowledge-based teams. Also, Network of Relationships plays a mediating role in the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance.

Keywords: Social Loafing, Team Performance, Network of Relationships

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of teams in organizations in order to benefit from synergy in teamwork and also to create the capacity to better adapt the organization to the environment is a trend that has gained increasing momentum in the last two decades (Wu & Kerdpitak, 2023). Effective teams are a vital factor. They are considered successful for many organizations (Lacerenza et al., 2018). As a social system, the team has irreplaceable functions both for the institutions and organizations that include it and for its members. Today, the effective use of teams allows organizations to do great things, which cannot be done by one person, and improve the performance of the organization by creating synergies (Van Knippenberg, Nishii & Dwertmann, 2020), while these teams may be more productive than individuals, there is considerable evidence that teams necessarily are not as productive as they seem. One of the negative aspects of teamwork is the tendency of people to put in less effort when working in a group, this phenomenon is known as Social Loafing. In other words, despite the positive aspects of team work that can help improve the performance of institutions and organizations, teams also have dark dimensions and negative functions. One of the issues that affect team productivity is the reduction of the conscious effort of individuals at the team level or Social Loafing (Karau & Wilhau, 2020). The tendency to work less in a collective environment can significantly negatively affect organizational performance and People's lives. Social Loafing is a deliberate attempt to try less in the team (Mihelič & Culiberg, 2019). Understanding Social Loafing in team activities is an important issue, because Social Loafing leads to a decrease in the performance of people in a team compared to when they act individually. Social Loafing is a hidden and dangerous phenomenon that, if not taken seriously, can destroy all the expected results. It is essential to reduce the problem of Social Loafing, especially in teams and working groups (Karau & Wilhau, 2020), and has considered abnormalities as an important issue that causes changes in attitude, vision, productivity and efficiency, a fundamental challenge.

In order to fill this challenge and prevent the evasion of people in the team, the trust between people should be stronger and the more people have access to the resources of the organization, they will show better performance and be encouraged to be more efficient and have more communication in the organization and do in teamwork. One of the factors that cause bonds between people in groups is called Network of Relationships. Network of Relationships can be recognized as a factor that plays a role in reducing Social Loafing; In other words, one of the most effective ways to increase team and group effectiveness is the amount of Network of Relationships. Based on the results of past research, Network of Relationships leads to higher team effectiveness; Because the existence of this network in the organization and team leads to more and easier access to the resources needed to improve performance and face the challenges facing the team (Furman & Buhrmester, 2009 and Partanen, Chetty & Rajala, 2014).

Also, considering that people avoid organizational work by using evasion in groups; They can cause risk to the Network of Relationships in the organization and especially the Network of Relationships. They also cause people to refrain from correlations and network relations in the structure of Network of Relationships and create challenges and negatively affect team relations and team interactions between people. On the other hand, the Network of Relationships variable itself, as a collective characteristic, is a by-product of other activities of the organization. Network of Relationships is a network of relationships and bonds based on interpersonal and intergroup social trust and the interactions of individuals with groups, organizations and social institutions,

which is associated with social solidarity and cohesion, which provides the necessary support for individuals and groups (Möller & Halinen, 1999), identifying a series of relationships that increase Network of Relationships and ultimately increase or decrease team effectiveness and group performance, gives a more accurate view. Network of Relationships is considered as a mediating variable in the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance. The statistical population of the current research is active teams in knowledge-based companies. In today's competitive world, only organizations that have the ability to plan with a competitive approach can remain in the competition scene. The use of work teams is also very important in this type of organization. For this reason, this research has been carried out among EdTech companies. Due to the lack of research conducted in the field of Social Loafing and its impact on Team Performance, this research seeks to investigate the impact of Social Loafing on Team Performance with the mediating role of Network of Relationships in knowledge-based companies.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND RESEARCH BACKGROUND

As stated at the beginning of the discussion, teams as a social system have irreplaceable functions both for the institutions and organizations that include them and for their members. Teams make organizations do great things that cannot be done by one person and improve the organization's performance by creating synergies (Van Knippenberg, Nishii & Dwertmann, 2020) and have social organizations, teams also have dark dimensions and negative functions (Fernandez & Rainey, 2017). In this research, Social Loafing has been introduced as one of the negative dimensions of team functionality. Also, the mediator role of Network of Relationships in between Social Loafing and Team Performance are expressed.

II.I. SOCIAL LOAFING

The term Social Loafing was first used by Latané, Williams & Harkins (1979) and they used this term to describe the phenomenon of reducing people's effort at work when they cooperate in a group. Social Loafing refers to a person's tendency to reduce effort and the actual form of effort reduction in group activity (Harkins, Latane & Williams, 1980). In fact, the word Social Loafing, dodging a task, is a fake name for a concept that indicates the abuse of a person who in a group, he performs a task, it is from the efforts of others, while he is not questioned (Kızrak & Öztürk, 2023). Social Loafing indicates that a large group of people have a lesser role in the production process when they work collectively, in other words, they can They have a greater role in the process when they work together, while they are more productive when they work alone.

Social Loafing is sometimes called free riding and it refers to the phenomenon that when people work in a group, they make less effort to achieve goals than when they work alone (Gabelica, De Maeyer & Schippers, 2022). Free riding occurs when individuals do not have equal amounts of work, but share the benefits of the group equally. Gabelica, De Maeyer & Schippers (2022) believe that both dodgers and free riders benefit equally from the group. Because the result of group performance is shared equally among all group members, regardless of their data (Karau & Wilhau, 2020). In literature, Social Loafing (disappearing in the crowd) is a phenomenon that people are not accountable and their efforts are not evaluated; Because the responsibility is spread among all the members of the group. Also, Social Loafing can be considered as the result of poor performance in a dynamic task. The types of symptoms of a poor work are lack of communication, lack of agreement, lack of coherence in the distribution of labor and wasted time due to non-work-related data (Soylu, 2019). Stouten & Liden (2020) points out that Social Loafing is a phenomenon in which people in team situations put in less effort compared to when they work alone.

Research shows that there are elements of Social Loafing in every team. In addition to reducing Team Performance, Social Loafing has other negative outcomes for groups. For example, Karau & Wilhau (2020) showed that loafing has a negative relationship with group cohesion, which in turn is related to performance, absenteeism, and group satisfaction. In their experimental research, researchers have found several factors in creating or intensifying Social Loafing in groups. These factors are placed in three groups, work characteristics, group characteristics, and individual perception characteristics. Some of the features of the work include: The non-distinctiveness of each person's work contribution (Moltzen, 2009) was obtained when a person perceives that his work is not distinguishable from the work of others; It means that their work is not seen, they reduce their efforts; Not defining the work is another well-known feature that causes people to avoid group work. If the work structures are not known to people, it will cause them to reduce their effort and avoid work more often (Salancik & Pfeffer, 1978); The lack of work standards has also been introduced as another reason for the reduction of people's effort, that people do not know what their work is and exactly what expectations and criteria are there to evaluate their performance; The lack of work motivation is one of the other factors that are known to reduce the effort and performance of people in a group (Salleh et al., 2016).

The lack of work motivation, which is one of the signs of the lack of difficulty in working goals, causes a decrease in people's efforts. The characteristics of the group which include: e. The large size of the group, which states that the larger the group size, the more people will reduce their effort. And. The lack of evaluation and supervision of people, which lack of evaluation and necessary controls by group leaders or organization managers, causes a decrease in the efforts of people in a team format. Also, the factors in a person's perceptual system include: h. The perception of avoidance of other members by the individual (Solu, 2019). There is a characteristic of individualism in people (in individualistic cultures, unlike collectivistic cultures, people tend to show less effort when they are working in a group). According to Bass (2104), among other individual factors, one can mention the perception of problems in the group's performance by the individual. If people observe that the group's performance is not appropriate and their effort may be wasted, they reduce its amount (Jerusalem & Schwarzer, 2014). The last factor that is rooted in the individual's perception is the existence of the perception of ability in related tasks by individuals. When a person perceives

that he is more effective in a task other than the assigned task, this perception causes or intensifies the phenomenon of Social Loafing (Tata, 2002).

II.II. TEAM PERFORMANCE

The fact is that teamwork is rapidly replacing traditional organizational methods in organizations, and the body of knowledge surrounding teamwork has grown tremendously over the past years, and many theories about Team Performance have emerged. But many similar approaches have been proposed to measure Team Performance. In this section, in order to achieve an operational definition, related researches are reviewed and finally, the impact of Social Loafing on the performance of work teams is presented. Evaluating the level of success of work teams is not an easy task due to the extremely human nature of teams, the word performance means doing a task or task. Wang & Ellinger (2011) states that organizational strategies, human resources, and the organization's external environment have the greatest impact on Team Performance. They considered performance at three individual, team, and organizational levels. The output and product characteristics of the team such as quality, quantity and timeliness, accuracy and cost are known as Team Performance.

On the other hand, the characteristics of teamwork processes such as skills, leadership, coordination and communication are defined as team effectiveness. But some researchers use Team Performance and team effectiveness interchangeably (Wang & Ellinger, 2011). However, one of the challenges of team researchers has always been to clarify what they mean by Team Performance. The vast literature on team evaluation is mixed with different dimensions of performance. Even team decision making is considered as a kind of performance. Another major criticism levelled at the vast literature on team analysis is that it has neglected what the team is supposed to do. Since what is supposed to be done is often largely ambiguous, it is not surprising that this literature usually focuses on processes. Kittur, Lee & Kraut (2009) said that team focus on the individual, but the work teams are built in a very explicit task structure, and most of the expert members and roles are divided into Interdependencies are determined by the requirements and necessities of the work to be done. Several guides through which the members' contribution to the team's results are determined have a significant impact on the patterns describing the team's performance and effectiveness.

In this regard, Stouten & Liden (2020) investigated the phenomenon of Social Loafing in team activities and concluded that among the factors affecting Social Loafing, only work-related characteristics have a significant impact on Social Loafing. Therefore, designing motivational work, creating work standards and giving identity to work are the main indicators that help to eliminate or reduce Social Loafing.

II.III. NETWORK OF RELATIONSHIPS

The term Network of Relationships was first proposed in 1977 by Mackworth, and the entry of this field into social sciences dates back to the 1990s, which led to its presence and entry into the field of organization and management studies (Mackworth, 1977). Network of Relationships is the total of real or potential resources that are created as a result of a durable network of familiarity and mutual recognition (Parks, 2017) that facilitates cooperation within and between groups. Lechner & Dowling (2003) define Network of Relationships as the total of potential and actual resources available within, accessible through and resulting from the "network" of relationships of an individual or social unit. They have listed three dimensions for Network of Relationships, which include: structural dimension, relational dimension, cognitive dimension; structural dimension: dimension refers to the general pattern of communication between agents; relational dimension: the type of personal relationships between people based on history. It describes their interactions with each other; the cognitive dimension: refers to the sources that provide interpretations, interpretations and systems of common meanings in groups (Ford et al., 2011).

According to Holmlund & Törnroos (1997), Network of Relationships has two components. First, it is a resource with which communication becomes possible through group membership and social networks, and second, the amount of Network of Relationships that a human agent possesses is based on the size of communication networks that he can mobilize membership in groups and being involved in social networks, which are obtained in groups, and the social relations resulting from being a member can be used in an effort to improve the social position of activists in various and different fields (Sandström & Carlsson, 2008).

Yu et al. (2022) consider Network of Relationships in the three dimensions of in group and outgroup and relational Network of Relationships. Mutual understanding and support that strengthens intragroup exchanges is a product of intragroup Network of Relationships that arises from the context of family ties, neighbourhood and friendship. Strengthening the connection to external resources and facilitating the dissemination of information are the two main functions of out-group Network of Relationships that is achieved through social networks and membership in non-local associations and groups. Finally, the access of individuals and groups to different governmental, non-governmental and commercial sectors depends on the amount of their communication networks, which refers to the relationship between individuals and the official power structure (Vezzali et al., 2017).

Also, Network of Relationships has many dimensions and components that are appropriate to the society's culture, components such as trust, participation in civil institutions, proper communication with others, commitment and responsibility, cooperation and group spirit and a sense of collective identity are considered in this context (Igarashi et al., 2008). Nevertheless, the main components of social trust, social cohesion and social participation, which are placed in an interactive relationship and each

reinforces the other, are considered to be the main components of Network of Relationships. These three components are also key concepts of sociology (Igarashi et al., 2008). Social trust is necessary for the formation of social bonds and transactions, and it creates cooperation and cooperation, and it is only in this state that it is able to solve problems and fulfill obligations despite the existence of differences (Barbalet, 2019). Social participation also refers to those voluntary activities through which members participate in affairs and participate directly or indirectly in shaping social life.

Regarding the importance of Network of Relationships, Fee & Gray (2022) investigated the explanation of Network of Relationships as a key lever in improving team effectiveness and came to the conclusion that Network of Relationships has a significant impact on team effectiveness and perceived organizational support through the occurrence of organizational citizenship behavior on Team effectiveness has an impact. Also, Zagenczyk & Powell (2023) investigated the impact of Network of Relationships communication on employees' teamwork. The result of their research showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between Network of Relationships and teamwork of employees. Teng & Luo (2015) conducted a study titled "Perceived Social Loafing, social interdependence, and team emotional tone on team learning performance". The results of their research showed that the emotional tone of the group mediates the relationship between Social Loafing and social interdependence on team productivity. Schippers (2014) investigated Social Loafing tendencies and Team Performance. The results of his research showed that if there is a high degree of duty and agreement in the team, the team members tend to compensate for loafing and social flexibility and the performance is distributed in a balanced manner. When loafing is low, task orientation becomes less important and agreement becomes the most important factor in Team Performance.

According to the contents expressed about the concepts of Social Loafing and Network of Relationships in relation to Team Performance, little research has been done in the field of Social Loafing and Team Performance. Also, the importance of teamwork has become a special necessity in today's organizations as a core competency, today's organizations are surrounded by dynamic environments and environmental uncertainties, if they do not follow the capabilities of team-oriented activities, they face serious threats to their survival. Therefore, attention to Team Performance is an important factor in the success and competitive advantage of organizations. The sample respondents of this research is the EdTech companies located in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India, which has defined one of its main concerns as creating the drive for creativity and innovation. One of the ways to achieve this can be paying attention to team-oriented processes and improving Team Performance. Therefore, the results obtained in this research and the solutions provided for managers of knowledge-based organizations have been applied due to the importance of knowledge and Network of Relationships in the value creation process. Therefore, the conceptual model of the research is as follows:

Figure 1. The conceptual model of the research

According to the conceptual model of the research, the assumptions of the current research are as follows:

- H01: Social Loafing has a significant impact on group performance.
- H02: Social Loafing has a significant impact on Network of Relationships.
- H03: Network of Relationships has a significant impact on Team Performance.
- H04: Network of Relationships mediates the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is descriptive-survey and correlational in terms of practical purpose, in terms of data collection method. Structural equation modeling was done using SmartPLS version 3 software to test the research hypotheses. The target population of the current research is the teams based in the few selected EdTech (Education Technology) companies located in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. The number of available companies located in Chennai according to naukri.com are 129. A convenient sample of

60 companies with one team from each company are selected for study. The respondents to the questions of the questionnaire are people who have at least three years of work experience and are at the management and expert level who are working in those selected companies. Therefore, three experts in each company (selected by available sampling) the questionnaire was distributed.

By calculating the average of respondents from each company, 180 questionnaires were used to analyze the findings. Questionnaire consist of two parts. The first part is related to general questions, which demographic information is a statistical sample and includes age, education level, service history. The second part of the questionnaire is questions related to research variables. The seven-point Likert scale (1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree) was used in the measuring scale.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS

In order to achieve convergent validity and correlation, composite reliability and mean variance tests were evaluated. Reliability higher than 0.7 along with average variance of at least 0.5 are two necessary conditions for convergent validity and correlation of a structure. Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the questionnaire along with the number of research questions, composite reliability and average variance are given separately for each variable in the table below. In this table, Cronbach's alpha coefficient and composite reliability for each of the variables are above 0.7 and the average variance is above 0.5, which is acceptable.

Table 1. Reliability Statistics

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	CR	AVE	Communality	R2
Network of Relationships	0.811	0.912	0.541	0.541	0.498
Social Loafing	0.863	0.893	0.520	0.520	---
Team Performance	0.779	0.828	0.538	0.537	0.509

Table 2 is another criterion for assessing divergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Divergent validity is acceptable when the AVE for each construct is greater than the shared variance of that construct and other constructs (the square of the correlation coefficients between constructs) in the model. According to the findings of the table below, there is divergent validity because the numbers of the main diameter, which are the square root of the AVE values, are larger than the underlying numbers, which are the values of the correlation coefficients between the constructs. Finally, it can be said that the measurement model has a good fit.

Table 2. Divergent Validity Results

Variables	1	2	3
(1) Network of Relationships	0.735	---	---
(2) Social Loafing	-0.699	0.721	---
(3) Team Performance	0.660	-0.655	0.733

In order to analyze the validity of the questionnaire and discover the constituent factors of each obvious variable, confirmatory factor analysis is used. The results of confirmatory factor analysis of research questionnaire items are summarized in Table 3. Factor loadings related to each of the constructs were significant at the 95% confidence level. Therefore, the studied constructs have high reliability in terms of validity. With the help of the factor load, it can be said which item has a greater contribution in measuring its hidden variable. Each questionnaire item that has a higher factor load has a greater power or contribution in measuring the related hidden variable. In Table 3, the factor loadings for each variable are given in the corresponding column. If these values are above 0.4, we do not need to remove them.

We also use the GOF criterion to check the overall fit of the model. This criterion is obtained according to the following equation. Two indicators, the average of the cumulative index and the average of the squared correlation coefficients between the structures are used (extracted from the table).

$$GOF = \sqrt{\text{Communality} * \text{R Square}} = 0.515$$

The test result for the model fit index is equal to 0.51. Since the minimum acceptable value for this index is 0.36, it can be claimed that the research model has a high and strong fit. Now it's time to test the significance of the hypotheses, which uses two partial indicators, path coefficient and t-value. The significance of path coefficients is checked by t-values. At the confidence level of 95%, if the statistical values of t are higher than 1.96, the hypothesis is confirmed, and if it is lower, the hypothesis is rejected. In Figs. 2 and 3, the research model, which includes the sub-hypotheses of the research, or in other words, the second structural equation of the research, in two cases, the estimation of path and significance coefficients are shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

Table 3. Results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (Path Coefficients)

Variables	Indicator	Factor Loading
Social Loafing	Q1	0.543
	Q2	0.728
	Q3	0.806
	Q4	0.778
	Q5	0.867
	Q6	0.704
	Q7	0.818
	Q8	0.413
Network of Relationships	Q9	0.760
	Q10	0.786
	Q11	0.664
	Q12	0.846
	Q13	0.827
	Q14	0.544
	Q15	0.792
	Q16	0.618
	Q17	0.652
	Q18	0.742
Team Performance	Q19	0.762
	Q20	0.712
	Q21	0.653
	Q22	0.679
	Q23	0.695

Figure 2 actually shows the value of path coefficient and determination coefficient and Figure 3 also shows the value of t statistic.

Figure 2. Path Coefficients

Figure 3. T-statistic Coefficients

According to the explanations given and the research model in figs. 2 and 3, the state of the hypotheses can be determined. The following table summarizes the results of research hypotheses.

Table 4. Results of Hypotheses Testing

Research hypotheses	Path coefficient	t value	Result
Social loafing has a significant impact on group performance.	-0.380	3.935	Supported
Social Loafing has a significant impact on Network of Relationships.	-0.700	18.294	Supported
Network of Relationships has a significant impact on Team Performance.	0.395	3.891	Supported

Hypothesis 1: It indicates the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance, according to the path coefficient of 0.380 and the obtained t-value of 3.935, the hypothesis is confirmed. Considering the negative sign of the path coefficient, it can be seen that the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance is negative.

Hypothesis 2: It indicates the relationship between Social Loafing and Network of Relationships, according to the path coefficient of 0.700 and the obtained t-value of 18.294, the hypothesis is confirmed. Considering the negative sign of the path coefficient, it can be seen that the relationship between Social Loafing and Network of Relationships is negative. Hypothesis 3: It indicates the relationship between Network of Relationships and Team Performance, according to the path coefficient of 0.395 and the obtained t-value of 3.891, the desired hypothesis is confirmed.

Hypothesis 4: indicates the mediating role of Network of Relationships in the relationship between Social Loafing and performance. According to the table below and using the Sobel test, this hypothesis is confirmed and Network of Relationships mediates the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance.

Table 5. Results of Fourth Hypothesis

Independent variable	Mediator	Dependent variable	VAF	t-value	Result
Social Loafing	Network of Relationships	Team Performance	0.421	7.57	Supported

V. DISCUSSION

The purpose of the present research was to investigate the impact of Social Loafing on Team Performance with regard to the mediating role of Network of Relationships. In the first hypothesis, it was stated that Social Loafing has a significant impact on team performance. According to the analysis of the obtained data, this hypothesis was confirmed. The obtained result is in accordance with the research of Schippers (2014); Ying et al. (2014); and Cicekdagi, Ayyildiz & Akkoyunlu (2023). The second hypothesis indicates the relationship between Social Loafing and Network of Relationships, which is confirmed according to the obtained path coefficients. The obtained result is in accordance with the research of Shiue, Chiu & Chang (2010). The third hypothesis also indicates the relationship between Network of Relationships and Team Performance, which hypothesis is confirmed. The obtained result is in accordance with the research of Schippers (2014). The fourth hypothesis indicates the mediating role of Network of Relationships in the relationship between Social Loafing and performance. According to the result of Sobel test, this hypothesis is confirmed and Network of Relationships mediates the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance. The obtained result is in accordance with the research of Ying et al. (2014).

The findings of this study showed that Social Loafing has a significant impact on Team Performance and Network of Relationships. Network of Relationships also has a significant impact on Team Performance. Also, Network of Relationships mediates the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance. Considering the obtained results and the negative impact of Social Loafing on Team Performance and Network of Relationships, it is necessary for the managers of knowledge-based companies to take measures to prevent employees' Social Loafing. Social Loafing at different levels can be a problem for organizations.

Considering that at the individual level there are factors such as internal motivation, lack of interest in work and duty, procrastinating personality, lack of desire to progress in the job, lack of evaluation of the individual's own progress, lack of personal goal setting and planning, lack of focus on the task and reduced accuracy in Work, perception of financial needs, perception of non-uniqueness of job and task are very important on the individual's motivation in Social Loafing, that's why it is very important to pay attention to employment policies and pay attention to the personality characteristics of people when they enter the organization.

At the team level, factors such as lack of understanding of cohesion, size exceeding the work capacity, hiding the individual in the crowd and consequently reducing the responsibilities in the team can be mentioned. For this reason, the attention of the managers of EdTech organizations and especially the team heads need to adhere to the rules of the teams and the proper division of tasks and establishing an atmosphere of trust among the members can affect the performance of the team.

Attention to organizational factors such as job dissatisfaction, organizational indifference, perception of unfairness of salaries, benefits and rewards, salary payment system, inefficient and ineffective reward, inefficient and ineffective performance evaluation system, use of wrong indicators in performance evaluation, proportionality between salaries, Benefits and rewards with individual performance, the perception of the organization's lack of trust in the individual's work, the perception of being ignored by team heads and managers, and an inappropriate work environment can also affect organizational performance and, accordingly, performance at the level of work teams, and increase Social Loafing.

As a result, in order to reduce social evasion, it is possible to refer to the management approach based on short-term and long-term. With special attention to the use of appropriate performance evaluation indicators, managers can create a more efficient and effective performance evaluation system and, as a result, a more efficient and effective salary and bonus payment system in their organization, and in this way, the perception of injustice in the payment of salaries and bonuses, and as a result, the perception of being neglected to reduce harassment by managers and team heads among employees in the organization. In this

way, people's external motivation increases and their Social Loafing decreases. In the short term, managers can reduce Social Loafing behavior with appropriate measures. For example, the managers' attention to the inappropriate work environment and its improvement in the short term reduces the job dissatisfaction of the employees and causes the Social Loafing behavior to decrease. According to the specific job description, managers can reduce the perception of confusion in the performance of tasks and the perception of delaying to do the work and reduce Social Loafing.

Also, considering the results obtained and the impact of Network of Relationships on Team Performance, the relationship between Social Loafing and Team Performance, paying attention to some actions can strengthen the Team Performance of individuals. Based on this result, increasing network links, network relations and promoting team homogeneity, trust, mutual obligations and expectations and common identity gives more power and courage to the members of the organization. This level of relationships and trust in each other's abilities and intentions provides the basis for the exchange of knowledge and experiences and will be accompanied by the creation of new knowledge by colleagues. In other words, the existence of norms, values, attitude, beliefs, culture, and common language due to its significant history can create a sense of identity and job importance in employees. Also, the existence of a wide network of relationships will also enable a wide range of employees to interact with each other. In general, this research shows that the expansion of Network of Relationships in EdTech companies plays a significant role in the development of organizational knowledge management. The existence of Network of Relationships in the organization and effective interactions between the organization's employees will facilitate the acquisition, creation and transfer of knowledge. In this regard, focusing on human resource management approaches can promote proper communication between employees, because human resource management practices can have a significant impact on organizational Network of Relationships among employees and increase Team Performance by reducing Social Loafing.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR THE FUTURE

Interpretation of the results presented here is subject to a number of limitations. First, in future research, it is desirable to pay attention to the separation of different industries and increase the number of responding companies in each industry. Second, since this research relies heavily on self-reported measurements by managers, future research works can provide more confidence in the obtained results by replacing direct objective measurements (instead of self-reporting method). However, in the case of Social Loafing, the alternative method can be insufficient because it may not be a fair reflection of the overall management of the enterprise environment due to its multidimensional nature. Third, it is suggested to investigate other factors affecting Team Performance in knowledge-based companies.

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